

Template Change Request - Simplified

Request ID:	
Change Requester:	Name of the person or team requesting the change
Approval Responsible:	Name of the PO, PM, or responsible stakeholder
Request Date:	Date the request was submitted
Affected System Version:	e.g., v1.2.0
Type of Change:	Bug fix, improvement, new feature, customization, other
Change Category:	FR (Functional Requirement), NFR (Non-Functional Requirement), interface, process, documentation, other
Detailed Description:	Explanation of the need and context
Change Impact:	Scope/Schedule/Cost
Does it impact existing requirements?	Yes/No
Impacted or related requirements:	Indicate related FRs or NFRs
Technically Feasible?	Yes/No
Acceptance Criteria:	How will we know the change has been implemented correctly?
Priority:	High/Medium/Low
Change Request Status:	Not started ▾